

Research Article

DOI: doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16785040

A MODIFICATION OF HYBRID CONJUGATE GRADIENT METHOD BASED ON MEMORYLESS BROYDEN'S UPDATE FOR NONLINEAR SYSTEMS OF EQUATIONS

Ahmed A. Lawal^{1*}, Abba V. Mandara², Usman A. Marte³; Ahmadu M. Musa⁴ and Hassan Habibu⁵

^{1,2,3,4,5} Department of Mathematics, Faculty of Physical Sciences, University of Maiduguri, Borno State, Nigeria.

*Corresponding author's Email Address: ahmadububakarlawal@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Conjugate Gradient (CG) methods are widely used for solving large-scale nonlinear systems of equations due to their efficiency in employing vector operations. Many articles developed different kinds of conjugate gradient coefficients. Recently, some conjugate gradients were proposed with large dimensions, but they have small sample sizes. So, they cannot solve problems that have higher dimensions. In this research, we propose a novel hybrid conjugate gradient method for nonlinear system of equations. The parameter β_k^{NHCG} is computed as a convex combination of β_k^{FR} and β_k^{RMIL} coefficients respectively. It satisfies a sufficient descent and converge globally under some suitable conditions. Numerical results of the hybrid algorithm show effectiveness in large scale unconstrained optimization problems.

Keywords: Hybrid Conjugate Gradient, Wolfe line search, Global Convergence Analysis.

INTRODUCTION

The nonlinear conjugate gradient (CG) method has played a special role in solving large-scale nonlinear optimization due to the simplicity of its iterations and low memory requirements. The CG method is the fastest and most robust optimization algorithms for nonlinear problems. The nonlinear conjugate gradient method is the extension based on the linear conjugate gradient method was first proposed by Hestenes and Stiefel in 1952 [1,2] for solving linear system equations. In 1964, Fletcher and Reeves [3,4] extended it to nonlinear problems and obtained the first nonlinear conjugate gradient method called FR method.

In this paper, we focus on nonlinear unconstrained optimization problem of finding $x \in R^n$ such that:

$$g(x) = 0, \quad (1)$$

where R^n is the n -dimensional Euclidean space and $g: R^n \rightarrow R^n$ is continuous. Throughout this paper, this problem corresponds to the optimality condition of a certain problem of minimizing: $R^n \rightarrow R$ which may not be easy when the dimension n is large, conjugate gradient methods can be efficient to solve problem (1). For any given point $x_o \in R^n$, a sequence $\{x_k\}$ is generated by the following recursive relation:

$$x_{k+1} = x_k + \alpha_k d_k. \quad k=0,1,2,3,\dots \quad (2)$$

Where x_k is the current iteration point, $\alpha_k > 0$ is a step size, and d_k is the search direction. The line search in the scalar form which will search along the d_k for the best x_{k+1} . The most common line search is the exact line search, which is given by the equations

$$f(x_k + \alpha_k d_k) = \min_{\alpha \geq 0} f(x_k + \alpha d_k). \quad (3)$$

The CG search direction, d_k is defined by

$$d_k = \begin{cases} -g_k & \text{for } k = 0, \\ -g_k + \beta_k d_{k-1} & \text{for } k \geq 1, \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

Where g_k denotes the gradient of $f(x)$ at the point x_k . $\beta_k \in \mathbb{R}$ is a scalar known as the CG coefficient. Some well-known formulas for β_k include:

$$\beta_k^{FR} = \frac{g_k^T g_k}{\|g_{k-1}\|^2} \tag{5}$$

$$\beta_k^{PR} = \frac{g_k^T (g_k - g_{k-1})}{\|g_{k-1}\|^2} \tag{6}$$

$$\beta_k^{HS} = \frac{g_k^T (g_k - g_{k-1})}{(g_k - g_{k-1})^T d_{k-1}} \tag{7}$$

$$\beta_k^{LS} = \frac{g_k^T (g_k - g_{k-1})}{-d_{k-1}^T g_{k-1}} \tag{8}$$

$$\beta_k^{DY} = \frac{g_k^T g_k}{(g_k - g_{k-1})^T d_{k-1}} \tag{9}$$

$$\beta_k^{CD} = -\frac{g_k^T g_k}{(d_{k-1}^T g_{k-1})} \tag{10}$$

$$d^{NHCG} = -(1 + \beta_k F^T d_k) F_{k+1} + \|F_{k+1}\|^2 \beta_k d_k$$

where

$$\beta_k = \mu_k^* (\beta_k^{FR} + (1 - \mu_k^*) \beta_k^{RML})$$

The above corresponding methods are known as Fletcher and Reeves [3], Polak-Ribiere [5], Hestenes and Steifel [6], Liu and Storey [7], Dai and Yuan [8], and finally, Conjugate Descent [8], respectively. We represent the norm of vectors as $\|\cdot\|$. For $f(x)$, which is strictly a convex quadratic function, all these methods will have finite convergence properties under the exact line search. But they behave quite differently [9-16] for general non-quadratic functions.

Andrei [17], has classified the Conjugate Gradient methods into three categories: First category (classical CG method), second category (Scaled CG), and finally, third category (hybrid and parameterized CG methods). The pioneer CGs are considered as the classical CG methods. Producing a CG of this category is difficult, but its applications are easy for such reasons, researchers came out with the scaled and hybrid CG methods. Some of the best research conducted on these types of CGs are R. Fletcher's practical method [8], Powell [18], Sun and Zhang [19], Yuan and Wei [20], Shi and Guo [21], Rivaie et al. [22]. and Usman and Ugr [23].

Therefore, in recent years, more efforts have been shifted towards modifying and constructing a new formula for CG methods with good numerical performance and global convergent properties. FR, DY, and CD, have strong convergence properties, but they may not perform well in practice due to jamming. On the other hand, although the second set of methods, PRP, HS and LS, may not converge in general. However, they often perform better than the classical methods. Consequently, combinations of methods have been proposed in some studies. Below, we list some of the proposed nonlinear CG methods. Perry et al [24] and suggest the following hybrid method;

Algorithm of β_k

A modified hybrid CG algorithm known as: β_k^{NHCG} is hereby introduced.

Algorithm (NHCGA)

Step 1: Given that $x_0 \in \mathbb{R}^n$, $\alpha_0 > 0$, $\epsilon = 10^{-6}$, $d_0 = F_k$, $k = 0$.

Step 2: Compute F_k .

Step 3: If $\|F_k\| \leq \epsilon$, then stop; else go to Step 4.

Step 4: Compute the step length α_k using (3.15)

Step 5: Set $x_{k+1} = x_k + \alpha_k d_k$.

Step 6: Compute F_{k+1} .

Step 7: Compute $\beta_k^{FR} = \frac{\|F_{k+1}\|^2}{2}$.

$$\text{Step 8: Compute } \beta^{RMIL} = \frac{k\|F_k\|}{k\|d_k\|^2} \frac{y_k^T F_{k+1}}{k\|d_k\|^2}.$$

Step 9: Update μ_k using (3.10)

Step 10 Update β_k by using (3.13)

Step 11: Compute d_{k+1} , by using (3.12)

Step 12: Set $k = k + 1$ and go to Step 3.

METHODOLOGY

In this research work, we denote $s_k = x_{k+1} - x_k$, $F_k = F(x_k)$. In this chapter, we propose a novel CG update parameter by incorporating an extension of the method in [15]. This is made possible by using the memoryless Broyden's update together with the hybrid direction of two CG parameters. The formula for Broyden's update is given by [25-26].

$$B_{k+1} = B_k + \frac{(y_k - B_k s_k) s_k^T}{s_k^T s_k} \quad (3.1)$$

where B_k is an $n \times n$ matrix, which is the Jacobian approximation at x_k . Nevertheless, [27] proposed the inverse of Broyden's update defined by

$$B_{k+1}^{-1} = B_k^{-1} + \frac{(s_k - B_k^{-1} y_k) y_k^T}{y_k^T y_k} \quad (3.2)$$

To obtain a matrix-free scheme, we approximate the matrix $B^{-1} \approx I + \gamma_k$, where I stands for the identity matrix and γ_k is a scalar. Thus becomes

$$B_{k+1}^{-1} = I + \gamma_k + \frac{(s_k - \gamma_k y_k) y_k^T}{y_k^T y_k} \quad (3.3)$$

and

$$B_{k+1}^{-1} = I + \gamma_k + \frac{s_k y_k^T}{\|y_k\|^2} - \gamma_k \frac{y_k y_k^T}{\|y_k\|^2} \quad (3.4)$$

Now adopting the Perry's [24] point of view, we can express the hybrid search direction of the FR and RMIL CG direction as

$$d_{k+1} = -M_{k+1} F_{k+1}, \quad (3.5)$$

Where:

$$M_{k+1} = I - \mu_k \frac{d_k F_{k+1}^T}{\|F_k\|^2} - (1 - \mu_k) \frac{d_k y_k^T}{\|d_k\|^2} \quad (3.6)$$

Termed as the search direction matrix obtained by a convex combination of the two CG parameters. Therefore, we can find the parameter μ_k as the solution of the following minimization problem.

$$\min_{\mu} \|\Delta_{F_{k+1}}\|^2 \quad \mu_k > 0, \quad (3.7)$$

where $\Delta_{k+1} = M_{k+1} - B_{k+1}^{-1}$ and $\|\cdot\|_F$ denotes the Frobenius matrix norm

and recalling the relation $\|\Delta\|_F = \text{trace}(\Delta^T \Delta)$, we get the following solution for (3.7) as described below;

$$\text{tr}(\Delta_{k+1} \Delta_{k+1})^2 = \|\Delta_{k+1}\|_F^2 \quad (3.8)$$

Thus, the trace of the terms containing the coefficient μ_k and μ^2 after simplification can be obtained as:

$$|\Delta_{k+1}|_F^2 = \mu_k^2 \left(\frac{(s_k^T F_{k+1})^2 + (s_k^T y_k)^2}{\|F_k\|^2 \|d_k\|^2} \right) - 2\mu_k \left(\frac{(s_k^T y_k)^2 - (s_k^T F_{k+1})(s_k^T y_k)}{\|F_k\|^2 \|d_k\|^2} \right) + \frac{1}{\|F_k\|^2} [s_k^T F_{k+1} - s_k^T y_k] + \frac{(s_k^T y_k)^2 - (s_k^T F_{k+1})(s_k^T y_k)}{\|F_k\|^2 \|d_k\|^2} + \frac{\gamma_k}{\|d_k\|^2} [s_k^T F_{k+1} - s_k^T y_k] \quad (3.9)$$

where τ is a real constant independent of μ_k including the terms $(-\mu^2)$, because it is always negative and since $\mu_k \in [0, 1]$.

More so, the computation of a second-degree polynomial of the variable μ_k , where the coefficient of μ_k , is always positive. Thus, the solution to (3.9) is given by

$$\mu_k^* = \frac{2}{(s_k^T F_{k+1})^2 + (s_k^T y_k)^2} \left(1 + \frac{\|F_{k+1}\|^2}{\|y_k\|^2} (s_k^T y_k)^2 - (s_k^T F_{k+1})(s_k^T y_k) + \|d_k\|^2 + (1 - \gamma_k)(s_k^T F_{k+1} - s_k^T y_k) \right) \quad (3.10)$$

Where γ_k is a scaling parameter adopted from Lemberger,

$$\gamma_k = + \frac{s_k^T y_k}{\|s_k\|^2} \quad (3.11)$$

Finally, based on the above derivations and to ensure that the sufficient descent condition is satisfied, the new search direction matrix can be defined as

$$d^{NHCG} = -(1 + \beta_k F^T d_k) F_{k+1} + \|F_{k+1}\|^2 \beta_k d_k, \quad (3.12)$$

where

$$\beta_k = \mu_k^* (\beta_k^{FR} + (1 - \mu_k^*) \beta_k^{RMIL}) \quad (3.13)$$

Where $\mu_k^* \in [0, 1]$

It is worth noting that when $\mu_k^* \in [0, 1]$ we have a perfect convex combination of FR and RMIL parameters. For the step-length computation α_k , we use the line search procedure presented by Li and Fukushima. Suppose that, $\psi_1 > 0, \psi_2 > 0$ and $t \in (0, 1)$ be constant and $\{\Omega_k\}$ a positive sequence such that:

$$\sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \Omega_k < \Omega < \infty. \quad (3.14)$$

Then the step length α_k can be computed as:

$$f_{k+1} f_k \leq \psi_1 \|\sigma_k F_k\|^2 - \psi_2 \|\sigma_k d_k\|^2 + \Omega_k F_k \quad (3.15)$$

where $f_k = f(x_k)$ defined (1.3) and F defined by (1.1). Let j_k be the smallest non-negative integer j such that

$$(3.15) \text{ holds for } \alpha_k = t^j$$

Convergence Analysis

The convergence result of NHC G algorithm is presented here based on the following assumptions on the function F .

To begin with, let us define the level set

$$\omega = \{x \in R^n: \|F(x)\| \leq \|F(x_0)\|^j\}, \quad (3.16)$$

Assumption 1

The level set ω defined by (3.16) is bounded, that is there exists a positive constant C , such that,

$$\|x\| \leq C \quad \forall x \in \omega. \quad (3.17)$$

Assumption 2

1. There exists $x^* \in R^n$, such that $F(x^*) = 0$.

a. F is continuously differentiable in a neighborhood of ω containing x^* .

Assumption 3

In some neighborhood N of ω , F is Lipschitz continuous, namely, there exists a constant $L > 0$ such that $\|F(x) - F(y)\| \leq L\|x - y\|, \forall x, y \in N.$ (3.18)

Properties (1) and (3) imply that there exists a positive constant N such that

$$\|F(x)\| \leq N, \forall x \in \omega, \tag{3.18}$$

However, it follows from Assumptions 1 and 3 that there exists a positive constant N , such that

$$\|F(x)\| \leq N, \text{ for all } x \in \omega. \tag{3.19}$$

Lemma 1 Let $\{x_k\}$ be generated by the NHCG algorithm, then d_{k+1} is a descent direction for F_{k+1} at x_k . i.e

$$F^T_{k+1} d_{k+1} < 0. \tag{3.20}$$

Proof: From (3.12), that is

$$d^{NHCG} = -(I + \beta_k F^T d_k) F_{k+1} + \|F_{k+1}\|^2 \beta_k d_k, \tag{3.21}$$

Multiply (3.21) by F_{k+1} to get

$$F^T_{k+1} d_{k+1} = -\|F_{k+1}\|. \tag{3.22}$$

Therefore, we conclude that

$$F^T_{k+1} d_{k+1} < 0. \tag{3.23}$$

Lemma 2. Suppose that Assumption 1 holds. Let $\{x_k\}$ be generated by the NHCG algorithm then $\{x_k\} \in \omega$. Proof: By Lemma 1, we have that $\|F_{k+1}\| \leq \|F_k\|$. Nevertheless, for all k we obtain

$$\|F_{k+1}\| \leq \|F_k\| \leq \|F_{k-1}\| \dots \leq \|F(x_0)\|$$

That is $\{x_k\} \in \omega$.

Lemma 3. Suppose Assumption 3 holds and the sequence $\{x_k\}$ is generated by the NHCG algorithm. Let $C > 0$ be a positive constant. if there exists $m, n > 0$ such that

$$\|F_k\|^2 \geq m, \quad \|d_k\|^2 \geq n, \tag{3.24}$$

Then,

$$|\beta_k| \leq NC. \tag{3.25}$$

That is, our new proposed β_k is bounded by some positive constant.

Proof: Let us consider (3.25), where we have:

$$\beta_k = \mu_k \frac{\|F_{k+1}\|^2}{\|F\|} + \frac{F^T_{k+1} y_k}{\|d_k\|^2} - \mu_k \frac{F^T_{k+1} y_k}{\|d_k\|^2} \tag{3.26}$$

Now, taking the absolute value of both sides

$$|\beta_k| \leq [\mu_k] \frac{\|F_{k+1}\|^2}{\|F\|} + \frac{|F^T_{k+1} y_k|}{\|d_k\|^2} - [\mu_k] \frac{|F^T_{k+1} y_k|}{\|d_k\|^2} \tag{3.27}$$

By applying the Cauchy-Schwarz inequality to obtain

$$|\beta_k| \leq [\mu_k] \frac{\|F_{k+1}\|^2}{\|F\|} + \frac{\|F_{k+1}\| \|y_k\|}{\|d_k\|^2} + [\mu_k] \frac{\|F_{k+1}\| \|y_k\|}{\|d_k\|^2} \tag{3.28}$$

From Assumption 3, we have:

$$|\beta_k| \leq [\mu_k] \frac{N^2}{m} + \frac{LN \|S_k\|}{n} + [\mu_k] \frac{LN \|S_k\|}{n} \tag{3.29}$$

Finally, we obtained

$$|\beta_k| \leq NC, \tag{3.30}$$

where $C = [\mu_k] \frac{N}{m} + (1 + \frac{[\mu_k] \|S_k\|}{n})$ and $\mu_k \in [0, 1]$, for all k .

This completes the Proof.

Theorem 1: [27] Suppose that Assumption 3 holds and $\{x_k\}$ is generated by the NHCG algorithm, then we have

$$\lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} \|\alpha_k d_k\| = 0, \tag{3.31}$$

$$\lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} \|\alpha_k F(x_k)\| = 0. \tag{3.32}$$

Proof: From (3.1) and (3.15), we have for all k.

$$\psi_2 \|\alpha_k d_k\|^2 \leq \psi_1 \|\alpha_k F(x_k)\|^2 + \psi_2 \|\alpha_k d_k\|^2, \tag{3.33}$$

$$\leq \|F(x_k)\|^2 - \|F(x_{k+1})\|^2 + \Omega_k \|F(x_k)\|^2. \tag{3.34}$$

By taking the sum of (3.33) and using (3.34)

$$\psi_2 \sum_{i=1}^k \|\alpha_i d_i\|^2 \leq \sum_{i=1}^k \|F(x_i)\|^2 - \|F(x_{i+1})\|^2 + \sum_{i=0}^k \Omega_i \|F(x_i)\|^2 \tag{3.35}$$

$$= \|F(x_0)\|^2 - \|F(x_{k+1})\|^2 + \sum_{i=0}^k \Omega_i \|F(x_i)\|^2 \tag{3.36}$$

$$\leq \|F(x_0)\|^2 - \|F(x_k)\|^2 + \sum_{i=0}^k \Omega_i \tag{3.37}$$

$$\leq N_2 + N_2 \sum_{i=0}^k \Omega_i \tag{3.38}$$

Numerical Experiment

This subsection presents a comprehensive performance analysis of the new hybrid CG algorithm (NHCG) across various problem instances. The conducted numerical experiments assess the robustness, computational efficiency, and convergence behavior of the new method across different problem sizes and characteristics. The study compares the performance of the new methods against a recent modifications of CG algorithm to evaluate its efficacy in terms of convergence speed (CPU time) and number of iterations.

To evaluate the performance of the proposed method the study conducted a numerical test on a collection of 100 unconstrained optimization test problems. For each testing problem, a range of dimensions that comprises small-scale as low as 1000 and large-scale dimensions up to 100,000 variables are considered. The accuracy of the computed solutions is assessed by comparing them against the following recent improved conjugate gradient method:

The Improved conjugate gradient method for nonlinear systems of equations [27] algorithm with dk computed using

All algorithms are implemented in MATLAB R2023a and run on a personal laptop with an Intel CORE i3 processor operating at 1.80GHz and 450 GB of RAM. The line search considered for the numerical computation is the procedure presented by Li and Fukushima, with the parameter values defined as follows: the values of $\psi_1 = \psi_2 = 10^{-4}$,

$$t = 0.2 \text{ and}$$

The termination criterion for all algorithms is set as

$$\|F(x_k)\| < 10^{-6}.$$

If any of the following holds:

$$\Omega_k = \frac{1}{(k+1)^2}.$$

1. The iteration number reaches 2000;
2. When $\|F_k\|$ is not a number (NaN).
3. Failure in the codes

Table 1: Numerical results based on dimension of problem (n), Number of iterations and CPU Time (in seconds) of problems 1-7

P	NHCG Algorithm			ICGB Algorithm			
	Dim	Iter	$\ F_k\ $	CPU time	Iter	$\ F_k\ $	CPU time
1	1000	4	1.6211e-06	0.00081	31	4.6201e-05	0.03119
	10000	3	1.8268e-06	0.00066	31	7.2022e-05	0.10898
	50000	4	1.0793e-06	0.00853	37	5.9132e-06	0.41489
	100000	6	2.2345e-06	0.00163	39	8.9241e-06	0.80703
2	1000	11	5.4647e-06	0.0051291	18	8.1857e-06	0.019647
	10000	11	4.0993e-06	0.006797	18	5.9288e-06	0.053642
	50000	11	5.1664e-06	0.007691	18	5.6441e-06	0.242161
	100000	12	5.5994e-06	0.029785	18	7.9820e-06	0.322754
3	1000	27	6.9265e-06	0.014515	76	9.4677e-06	0.061587
	10000	28	6.8690e-06	0.059455	78	8.9246e-06	0.224129
	50000	31	8.6013e-06	0.240648	81	8.9051e-06	1.051879
	100000	32	6.8119e-06	0.430044	81	9.6236e-06	1.857360
4	1000	16	8.1120e-07	0.009855	20	6.3527e-08	0.010461
	10000	19	6.4329e-07	0.035541	22	7.1739e-08	0.045256
	50000	19	6.5126e-08	0.135590	22	3.6882e-08	0.190270
	100000	19	6.0688e-08	0.261424	22	5.2159e-08	0.36712
5	1000	15	4.6340e-07	0.008503	76	7.5054e-06	0.029104
	10000	15	5.8615e-07	0.0037034	77	9.6216e-06	0.039770
	50000	17	5.2427e-07	0.0043230	76	5.5932e-06	0.180076
	100000	19	7.4143e-07	0.0024368	83	7.9100e-06	0.350064
6	1000	12	2.6828e-05	0.005975	17	2.1584e-06	0.011010
	10000	12	1.3292e-05	0.0125098	17	6.8254e-06	0.040440
	50000	13	4.2083e-05	0.111580	19	5.4749e-06	0.154925
	100000	13	3.3657e-05	0.09006	19	7.7426e-06	0.555382
7	1000	14	9.7928e-07	0.060383	51	6.9910e-06	0.007176
	10000	15	9.4715e-07	0.216088	52	6.9910e-06	0.068942
	50000	14	9.6823e-07	0.786077	53	8.9910e-06	0.614886
	100000	14	9.6419e-07	1.479564	52	9.5775e-06	1.136529

Table 2: Numerical results based on dimension of problem (n), Number of iterations and CPU Time (in seconds) of problems 8-10

NHCG Algorithm				ICGB			
P	Dim	Iter	$\ F_k\ $	CPU time	Iter	$\ F_k\ $	CPU time
8	1000	45	8.5992e-05	0.034983	39	5.0179e-07	0.039739
	10000	20	9.1045e-07	0.080477	53	5.8972e-07	0.228211
	50000	23	9.0727e-07	0.396575	184	9.8877e-07	3.811658
	100000	9	7.7739e-06	0.409578	65	6.9965e-07	2.735592
9	1000	10	7.3224e-07	0.007216	85	9.5750e-07	0.561622
	10000	37	8.8631e-07	0.068108	75	9.3339e-07	0.531271
	50000	42	8.3241e-07	0.131232	37	9.6663e-07	0.8457319
	100000	22	8.7128e-07	0.124679	105	9.9467e-07	2.177488
10	1000	11	9.1535e-07	0.009544	22	4.7435e-07	0.0110289
	10000	12	6.2523e-07	0.031216	23	8.2750e-06	0.0193011
	50000	12	8.3884e-07	0.0134385	23	1.8503e-06	0.526861
	100000	13	7.1178e-07	0.2603051	23	2.6168e-06	0.339827

Figure 1: Comparison of the performance of NHCG and ICGB methods as the dimension increases (in term of number of iterations).

Figure 2: Comparison of the performance of NHCG and ICGB methods as the dimension increases (in terms of CPU time).

DISCUSSION

The algorithm with the best performance will have its convergence curve lying at the top of the performance profile curve. The graphically presented results (see; Fig. 1) follow from the computational results demonstrated in Tables 1-2. The plot shows the reduction in the residual norm over CPU time and iterations number indicating rapid convergence to the solution.

From the left-hand side of Fig. 1, NHCG method won 65% and solved 100% of the problems successfully, then ICGB method which win 45% and solved 100% of the problems.

Fig.2 shows a very wide gap between the NHCG and the ICGB with NHCG algorithm winning 95% with ICGB winning only 10% from the left-hand side of the curve. The interpretation shows that NHCG and ICGB methods perform better on this metric.

Based on the numerical results presented in Tables 1 and 2, and the above discussion, it will suffice to say that the proposed NHCG algorithm is not only efficient and robust, but also very promising for the 100 benchmark problems considered.

CONCLUSION

In this research, we present a novel hybrid conjugate gradient method using memory-less Brayden's (NHCG) update, for solving a large-scale system of nonlinear equations and compare its performance with that of an improved conjugate gradient method for nonlinear systems of equations (ICGB). We, therefore, proved the convergence of the proposed method, using a back-tracking type line search. Finally, the numerical results show that, the proposed method is very efficient, accurate and robust.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

The authors wish to express their heartfelt appreciation to the referees for their comprehensive work and recommendations for further research.

REFERENCES

1. estenes MR, & Stiefel E. Methods of Conjugate Gradients for Solving Linear Systems. *Journal of Research of the National Bureau of Standards*. 1952;49(6), 409-436.
2. Mirhoseini N, Babaie-Kafaki S, & Aminifard Z. A Nonmonotone Scaled Fletcher-Reeves Conjugate Gradient Method with Application in Image Reconstruction. *Mathematical Sciences*. 2022;16(4), 389-404.
3. Fletcher R, & Reeves CM. Function Minimization by Conjugate Gradients. *The Computer Journal*. 1964;7(2), 149-154.
4. Huang YY, Liu SY, Du XW, & Dong XL. A Globally Convergent Hybrid Conjugate Gradient Method and Its Numerical Behaviors. *Journal of Applied Mathematics*. 2013;2013, 1-14.
5. Polak E, Ribière G. Note sur la Convergence de Méthodes de Directions Conjuguées. *Revue Française d'Informatique et de Recherche Opérationnelle*. 1969;3(16), 35-43.
6. Liu Y, Storey C. Efficient Generalized Conjugate Gradient Algorithms, Part 1: Theory. *Journal of Computational and Applied Mathematics*. 1992;69(1), 129-137.
7. Dai YH, & Yuan Y. Nonlinear Conjugate Gradient Methods. Shanghai: Shanghai Science and Technology Publisher; 2000.
8. Fletcher R. Practical Methods of Optimization. Vol. 1: Unconstrained Optimization. New York: Wiley; 1987.
9. Yakubu UA, Kankarofi RH, Sulaiman IM, Mamat M, Saputra MPA, Sukono. Fertilizer Transportation Problem Using Vogel Approximation Method. *IOP Conference Series: Materials Science and Engineering*. 2021;1115(1):012005.
10. Dai YH, Yuan Y. Nonlinear Conjugate Gradient Methods. Shanghai: Shanghai Science and Technology Publisher; 1998.
11. Yuan G, Wei Z. Conjugate Gradient Method of Nonlinear Problems. *Journal of Software Engineering and Applications*. 2010;3(6):503-509.
12. Yuan Y, Sun W. Theory and Methods of Optimization. Beijing: Science Press of China; 1999.
13. Zoutendijk G. Nonlinear Programming Computational Methods. In: Abadie J, editor. Integer and Nonlinear Programming. Amsterdam: North-Holland; 1970. p. 37-86.
14. Mandara AV, Mamat M, Waziri MY, Afendee MM. A Modification of Conjugate Gradient Method Using Strong Wolfe Line Search. *International Journal of Engineering and Technology*. 2018;7(3.28):163-167.

15. Sulaiman IM, Usman AY, Mamat M. Application of Spectral Conjugate Gradient Methods for Solving Unconstrained Optimization Problems. *International Journal of Optimization and Control: Theories & Applications*. 2020;10(2):198-205.
16. Usman AY, Mamat M, Mohamad AM, Sukono, Rivaie M. Modification on Spectral Conjugate Gradient Method for Unconstrained Optimization. *International Journal of Engineering and Technology*. 2018;7(3.28):307-311.
17. Andrei N. An Unconstrained Optimization Test Functions Collection. ICI Technical Report 13/08. Bucharest: Institute of Mathematical Statistics and Applied Mathematics; 2008.
18. Powell MJD. Convergence Properties of Algorithms for Nonlinear Optimization. *SIAM Review*. 1986;28(4):487-500.
19. Sun J, Zhang J. Global Convergence of Conjugate Gradient Methods Without Line Search. *Annals of Operations Research*. 2001;103(1-4):161-173.
20. Yuan G, Wei Z. New Line Search Methods for Unconstrained Optimization. *Journal of the Korean Statistical Society*. 2009;38(1):29-39.
21. Shi ZJ, Guo J. A Conjugate Gradient Method for Nonlinear Equations. *Journal of Computational and Applied Mathematics*. 2009;224(1):444-457.
22. Rivaie M, Fauzi M, Mamat M, Ismail M. A New Class of Conjugate Gradient Coefficient with Global Convergence Properties. *AIP Conference Proceedings*. 2012;1482(1):486-491.
23. Usman AY, Ugur Y. Necessary and Sufficient Conditions for First Order Differential Operators to be Associated with a Disturbed Dirac Operator in Quaternionic Analysis. *Advances in Applied Clifford Algebras*. 2015;25(1):1-12.
24. Perry A. A Modified Conjugate Gradient Algorithm. Discussion Paper No. 229. Evanston: Center for Mathematical Studies in Economics and Management Science, Northwestern University; 1976.
25. Touati-Ahmed D, Storey C. Efficient Hybrid Conjugate Gradient Techniques. *Journal of Optimization Theory and Applications*. 1990;64(2):379-397.
26. Gilbert JC, Nocedal J. Global Convergence Properties of Conjugate Gradient Methods for Optimization. *SIAM Journal on Optimization*. 1992;2(1):21-42.
27. Waziri MY, Yusuf A, Abubakar AB. Improved Conjugate Gradient Method for Nonlinear System of Equations. *Computational and Applied Mathematics*. 2020;39(4):321.